

THE STORY "MOLOCH" IN THE CONTEXT OF THE WORK OF A.I. KUPRIN

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Abstract. *The story "Moloch" occupies a key place in the oeuvre of A.I. Kuprin, since it was first published in 1896 and drew the attention of readers and critics to the author, the image embodied in the central character of the story "Moloch" will become a favorite in many of Kuprin's subsequent works, up to "The Duel". Following "Moloch", there are works that brought the writer to the forefront of Russian literature - "The Army Ensign", "Olesya", "At the Circus", "Horse Thieves", "The White Poodle" and the story "The Duel". In all of them, socio-cultural and ideological-moral issues come to the fore.*

Keywords: *story, hero, portrait, theme, issues, metaphor, symbol.*

INTRODUCTION

Alexander Ivanovich Kuprin, like his contemporary Maxim Gorky, gained invaluable life experiences through various "universities" and utilized the knowledge acquired from diverse environments such as the military, circus, and factory workers in his captivating stories and novels. Kuprin's works vividly reflect his tumultuous dreams, frequent changes in "specialties" and positions, numerous travels across the country, and a plethora of new encounters. In the mid-1890s, Kuprin penned a series of poignant essays depicting the plight of workers, simultaneously shaping the contours of his first major work – the novel "Moloch".

This novel marked the beginning of Kuprin's distinctive prose style, which, according to Bunin, featured an "apt and generously expressive language without excess". Thus, the rapid creative flourishing of Kuprin commenced, who crafted most of his most significant works at the turn of the 20th century. Following the success of "Moloch," Kuprin produced a succession of masterpieces that solidified his position among the literary giants of Russian literature, including "Army Ensign" (1897), "Olesya" (1898), "In the Circus" (1901), "Horse Thieves" (1903), "White Poodle" (1903), and the story "The Duel" (1905).

The period during which "Moloch" was written coincided with the most resounding triumphs of Russian capitalism, exemplified by the renowned All-Russian Industrial Exhibition in Nizhny Novgorod, vividly described by Gorky in his exceptional correspondence. This era also witnessed the active demonstrations of the growing and self-aware Russian proletariat. These momentous events did not escape the keen observation of Kuprin. Profoundly disturbed by the sight of a capitalist factory consuming human lives, Kuprin dedicated his story to this deeply troubling subject.

The theme of capitalist exploitation was not entirely new in the literature of that time. Several of Kuprin's contemporaries, such as P.D. Boborykin and D.N. Mamin-Sibiryak, portrayed large manufacturers and industrialists amassing immense profits while considering themselves the architects of culture and progress, each in their own unique way.

As A. Bayborodin astutely notes, "according to Alexander Kuprin, technological progress – truly the Moloch of technocracy, the Beast of the Apocalypse – in a tragically climactic development will break out of human hands to kill the soul in a person, then the flesh" [1].

The central character of the story, engineer Bobrov, endures the monstrous injustice of the surrounding reality with genuine tragedy. He finds himself enmeshed in the machine of capitalist progress, a mere cog in its complex mechanism.

Despite being a good and honest man, Bobrov suffers because he is engaged in a business he deeply despises. He possesses an intimate understanding of the devastating toll capitalist progress exacts on the tens of thousands of workers who toil in its service. Having calculated "that working in mines, metal factories and large factories shortens the life of a worker by about a whole quarter", Bobrov reaches the grim conclusion that every two days of work at the factory where he is employed "devours a whole person". This haunting realization gives rise to the image of the bloodthirsty ancient god Moloch, a potent symbol embodying the cruelty and inhumanity of capitalism that permeates the entire work.

Kuprin's story "Moloch" poignantly illustrates the inhumanity and cruelty of capitalism at its zenith. Bobrov's protest against this system, however, lacks practical significance due to his weak, neurotic, and characterless nature, rendering him incapable of fighting or taking action. His angry tirades are vulnerable, sometimes devolving into a denial of technology, culture, and civilization and a naive glorification of the "good old days" when ancestors traveled slowly and prayerfully with ample provisions. This weakness in Bobrov's position is evident.

The central theme of "Moloch" is the portrayal of capitalism's ruthlessness during its greatest "successes". It is no wonder that Moloch and Kvashnin merge together in Bobrov's mind, as he perceives Kvashnin as a "bloody, ugly, and menacing deity, like those idols of oriental cults, under whose chariots fanatics drunk with ecstasy rush during religious processions". Bobrov trembles with impotent rage at this realization [2, p. 75].

Kuprin's description of Bobrov's appearance highlights both his "large, white, beautiful forehead" and a smile that lends "charm to his, in fact, ugly face". Bobrov's eyes become "gentle and cheerful" when he laughs, revealing contrast to Kvashnin's portrayal.

In contrast, Kvashnin's portrait emphasizes features that underscore the rudeness and baseness of his nature. The all-powerful plant owner is described sitting in an armchair, "spreading his colossal legs and sticking out his stomach". He wears a round felt hat, his fiery hair shining from underneath. Kvashnin's actor-like shaven face, with sagging cheeks and a triple chin dotted with large freckles, appears sleepy and dissatisfied, his lips forming a contemptuous, sour grimace. Kuprin does not mention Kvashnin's eyes, instead focusing on detailing every pose and movement of his bulky body. Kvashnin is depicted hesitating to descend, standing behind a glass wall, "towering his massive figure over the group crowding around the car; with legs wide apart and a squeamish mien on his face, he looks like a Japanese idol of rough work" [2, p. 40].

It is characteristic that in this scene, where Kvashnin first appears, the writer compares him to an idol, foreshadowing the Kvashnin-Moloch parallel that emerges in the story's finale. This juxtaposition resurfaces repeatedly throughout the narrative. Bobrov notices on Nina's face, as she looks at Kvashnin, "that smile and the same anxious fear of a savage gazing upon his idol" [2, p. 40]. However, the workers' wives' approach Kvashnin with their grievances: "As soon as Vasily Terentyevich, clutching the box with his hands, grunting and tilting the entire carriage, stepped onto the running board, the women swiftly surrounded him from all sides and fell to their knees...

Initially, Kvashnin couldn't discern anything: the women were shouting simultaneously and holding out their babies to him". The image of women kneeling before the owner and presenting their children to him involuntarily evokes an association with the honors bestowed upon the bloodthirsty Moloch, who accepts human sacrifices, as Bobrov had mentioned.

Kuprin placed great significance on the portrayal of Kvashnin. Specifically, he notes: "Two other workers, standing at the top and also ceaselessly working, threw down increasing piles of coal, which towered in immense black shafts around the boiler room. Bobrov perceived something oppressive and inhuman in the stokers' endless toil. It appeared as though some supernatural force had chained them to these gaping mouths for eternity, and they, under the threat of a terrible death, had to tirelessly feed and nourish the insatiable, voracious monster..." [2, p. 48]. It must be said that this is Kuprin's greatest achievement. Interestingly, when initially publishing *Moloch* in *Russian Wealth*, Kuprin, at Mikhailovsky's request, made several censorship-related corrections, particularly softening Kvashnin's image. Later, while preparing the text for the "Stories" collection, Kuprin made amendments and additions, further sharpening Kvashnin's characterization. His figure acquired even more striking and repulsive features in the final version. In the first printed version, Kvashnin, upon seeing Nina Zinenko from the carriage window and immediately becoming interested in her, conducted his conversation about her with the plant director Shelkovnikov in French, giving it the character of small talk. In the final text of the story, Kvashnin initiates the conversation about Nina with a rude, dismissive treatment.

This question, uttered through clenched teeth, with utter contempt for both the interlocutor and the person in question, quite clearly defines the nature of the entire subsequent conversation about Nina and the goal pursued by Kvashnin in seeking her acquaintance.

Kvashnin's attitude towards the workers who serve his factories and contribute to his wealth is particularly important.

Kuprin adds scenes that clearly represent this perspective, such as the "babi riot" episode in the first printed edition. In this scene, Kvashnin, besieged by the wives of workers protesting against poor housing conditions, hypocritically promises to build furnaces and cover barracks with lumber. Kuprin significantly enhances this episode in the separate edition, revealing that Kvashnin's behavior is a well-calculated tactic.

Kvashnin's cynicism, unbridled rudeness, and disregard for moral norms stem not only from his sense of impunity but also from his belief that he and his ilk are the "salt of the earth", a group of "chosen ones" to whom "everything is allowed". His speech at the picnic is characteristic of this mindset.

However, Kuprin goes beyond merely presenting Kvashnin's "credo". He demonstrates how this "creed" crumbles when confronted with reality.

Despite declaring himself the "chosen one of the nations" and boldly commanding the crowd, Kvashnin turns pale with fear at the first news of riots at the plant. He sends a telegram to the governor requesting assistance and then cowardly hurries to retreat.

The portrayal of the workers in the story is crucial. Initially, the story concluded with a depiction of a workers' uprising, but censorship forced Kuprin to change the ending. He retained only a mention of the uprising, focusing mainly on Bobrov's experiences and excluding the actual scene.

In other episodes featuring workers, criticism suggests that the writer primarily saw humility and meekness in them. This conclusion is based on the scene of a solemn prayer service

celebrating the opening of a new blast furnace. In this scene, workers are depicted as "big children" "with courageous and simple hearts" and as "humble warriors" who daily leave "their dank, alert dugouts for the usual feat of patience and courage" [2].

The character embodied in the central figure of "Moloch" becomes a favorite in many of Kuprin's subsequent works, up to "The Duel."

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, A.I. Kuprin's story "Moloch," first published in 1896 in the magazine "Russian Wealth," was the writer's first major work. It drew the attention of readers and critics to the author. Kuprin's Moloch served as a special stage in the development of the theme of capitalism's influence on Russian reality, reflecting the social realities of the turn of the century.

The main events unfold against the backdrop of the factory, metaphorically likened to the mythical image of the ancient idol Moloch – a bloodthirsty creature devouring human lives and constantly demanding new victims. This allows the author to actualize the idea of the domination of bourgeois civilization.

REFERENCES

1. Bayborodin A. Moloch of technocracy and its priests. The visionary providence of Alexander Kuprin // Literature Day // denliteraturi.ru
2. Kuprin A.I. Moloch // Kuprin A.I. Moloch; Duel; Stories. – M.: Pravda, 1985. – 480 p.